

Resource Allocation Ensuring Physical Layer Security in Cooperative Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access in 6G Networks

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Abstract—Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access (NOMA) is a potential candidate for 6th Generation (6G) cellular communication. It outperforms the conventional Orthogonal Multiple Access (OMA) schemes in terms of connectivity, spectral efficiency and latency. In spite of these advantages, NOMA faces information security challenges. In this paper, two phases of NOMA are considered which are the direct transmission phase and the cooperative phase. In the direct transmission phase, all users receive the superimposed signal while in the cooperative phase the user with a higher channel condition helps the user with the weaker channel condition. In the proposed work, the secrecy rate of users with weaker channel conditions is considered for maximisation under total power and Quality-of-Service (QoS) constraints. Our results show an improvement in the secrecy rate.

Index Terms—Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access, Quality-of-Service, Secrecy Rate, Physical Layer Security, optimization

I. INTRODUCTION

Multiple Access (MA) techniques are used in communication systems to enable a large number of users to access common channel resources [1], thus increasing channel capacity [2]. MA schemes used so far are based on orthogonality to identify the original message and to eliminate interference from other users. These MA techniques are called conventional Orthogonal Multiple Access schemes. MA schemes play a very important role in the different generations of wireless communication. Presently, with the concept of the Internet of Things (IoT), the number of smart devices, such as cell phones, tablets, wearable sensors, home appliances, vehicular networks etc., are being increased [3]. Similarly, mobile communication trends like devices explosion (from billions to trillions), super-fast hyper-connectivity, cost-effectiveness, and giga-services demand (motivated by virtual reality, Hologram and Ultra-high definition) tend to be increased much more by 2030. These mobile communication trends result in high data rates, massive connectivity and more bandwidth requirements. These requirements of tremendous connectivity

and high data rates have direct effects on the bandwidth of the whole system, and these demands can not be fulfilled with the present 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) mobile communication standards. In order to fulfil the data requirements, the next generation of cellular communication needs to be implemented which can be expected to provide enhancement in total system capacity i.e. thousands of times more smart mobile devices, thousands of times more data traffic, and lowest latency with more efficient energy utilization.

Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access (NOMA) is one of the candidates that are considered for 6G and beyond wireless communication systems due to better utilization of available resources, low latency, and massive connectivity. NOMA can further be categorized into two main domains; Code-based NOMA (C-NOMA) and Power-based NOMA (P-NOMA). The main difference between C-NOMA and Code Division Multiple Access (CDMA) is that CDMA works on dense codes whereas C-NOMA works on sparse codes. Users are separated in P-NOMA based on their power allocation factor, which is dependent on the placement of the users with respect to the base station (BS). The nearer the user the greater the average channel gain and the lesser will be the power allocation factor. Similarly, the farther the user the lower the average channel gain will be and greater power allocation will be assigned. Both the users are superimposed then and broadcast to the user network. At the receiver end, the user with a lower power factor will be facing a huge interference caused by the higher power factor user. So, the user with a better channel condition will first detect the signal of the user with a higher power factor. The detected signal will then have vanished from the received signal through Successive Interference Cancellation (SIC).

Besides all these benefits of NOMA, the superposition nature leads legitimate users to safety dreads. The security apprehension still needs to be addressed. Although the superposition nature makes the research community deliberate

about safety, it also allows us to use one user as a relay to help the other. Both points are taken into consideration, and a system model is proposed in this paper in which power resources are optimized, ensuring physical layer security in the cooperative nature of NOMA. The cooperative nature of NOMA presented in this paper is different from the other conventional cooperative techniques. We proposed that signal of the weaker user detected by the stronger user in the SIC process can be used to help the weaker user in the presence of an eavesdropper.

The rest of the article is structured as follows. Section II gives a brief review and comparison of existing works on cooperative NOMA and physical layer security. Section III includes the system model. Section IV includes the derived equations and the algorithm for the secrecy rate maximization. Results are discussed in section V and finally, the article is concluded in section VI.

II. RELATED WORK

Due to the broadcast nature of wireless communication, the physical layer is the first layer to exploit random channel gain. As multiple users are superimposed while utilizing the common resources, preserving the security of individual users becomes of paramount importance in NOMA. Several notable works have been proposed in the literature to provide secure and reliable communication for NOMA users. A secure Cooperative NOMA model is presented for Nakagmi-m fading channels in [4]. The authors considered two User Equipments (UEs), a relay and a BS. The communication is taking place in the presence of an eavesdropper and secrecy capacity has been found for both Amplify-and-Forward (AF) and Decode-and-Forward (DF) relaying systems. In the presented work no direct transmission phase between BS and UEs are considered. Narasimha et al. [5] considered a cooperative NOMA network with a hybrid relaying system (Decode-Amplify Forwarding) for enhancement of physical layer security. The system model considered has a BS, two relays, two users, and an eavesdropper. Users are communicating with BS without having a direct link between them. The communication takes place via a hybrid relay assuming a jammer node that introduces the interference for the eavesdropper. Secrecy rate analysis has been done in both AF and DF scenarios. C. Gong et al. [6] improved the security in large-scale NOMA with the help of Artificial Noise (AN). The system model comprises BS at the centre with UEs randomly distributed in a circular fashion. One of the mobile users is responsible for the generation of AN to the eavesdropper. The expressions for the secrecy capacity have been founded and discussed. Similarly, Y. Ren et al. [7] presented secured cooperative NOMA, with no direct link between UEs and BS. The communication takes place through Full-Duplex (FD) relay and an eavesdropper is placed between the BS and relay. In this model, the relay has two antennas, one is used for receiving and transmitting the data and the other

is introducing the AN to the eavesdropper. Similar work has been reported in [8] by B. Chen et al., considering the eavesdropper exploiting any of the channels regardless, between the BS to relay or between relay to the UEs. Further to this work, secrecy outage probability (SOP) expressions are derived and discussed. Similarly, secrecy performance analysis in NOMA cooperative network has been carried out by B. Su et al. [9]. The authors considered a system having BS and a relay communicating with the two UEs, and one of the UEs acting as an eavesdropper for the other one.

In one of the most recently published work by M. Li et al. [10], vehicle and pedestrian network is considered for improving security through the Ambient Radio Frequency (RF) concept. The Outage probability expression is derived and discussed in the paper. Huabo et al. [11] worked recently on the physical layer security in Unmanned Air Vehicles (UAV) - Aided NOMA. In this work, the authors secure the downlink communication of legitimate users by the power splitting technique. Some of the power is allocated to the information signal and some are allocated to the artificial noise. The minimum secrecy rate is maximized in this work. In [12] Y. Dursun and Z. Ding have worked on the secrecy rate maximization in uplink Multiple Input Multiple Output (MIMO) - NOMA through the singular decomposition method under the constraints of total power and Quality-of-Service (QoS). Furthermore, the secrecy rate is maximized in [13] in Multiple Input Single Output (MISO) - NOMA with the help of a backscatter device in the presence of an active eavesdropper using the Symbiotic Radio system.

The comparison of the literature in section II is summarized in table I. In all of the above-mentioned literature, the cooperative nature of the NOMA in which strong users cooperate with weak users is not considered for physical layer security. In this paper, users with greater channel conditions are considered two phases of Downlink-NOMA (D-NOMA) communication. 1st phase is the direct transmission phase and 2nd is the cooperative phase, where a stronger user act as a relay and helps the user with weaker channel condition. Furthermore, this paper presents the secrecy rate maximization of the cooperative NOMA in the downlink scenario.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM MODEL FOR DOWNLINK NOMA

The proposed system model consists of two users, one BS located in the centre and one eavesdropper. The proposed system model has two transmission phases, the direct transmission phase, and the cooperative phase. Suppose UE_1 is the user with a weaker channel gain which depicts UE_1 is the farthest user from the BS, and UE_2 is the nearest user or the user with a stronger channel gain as shown in Fig.

TABLE I
COMPARISON OF THE PROPOSED AND RELATED WORK

Reference	Physical-Layer Security	Cooperative	Link between BS and UE	Link between Relay and UE	Artificial Noise	Resource Optimization
[4]	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	No
[5]	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Jammer introducing the interference to eavesdropper	Yes (through Differential Evolution Based Algorithm)
[6]	Yes	Yes (legitimate users help each other in enhancing physical layer security by introducing interference to the eavesdropper)	Yes	No	Noise is generated by the legitimate users itself, UEs are full-duplex	No
[7]	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes (Relay is responsible to introduce Artificial Noise)	Not at BS but at Relay through energy harvesting
[8]	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Interference signal is introduced by user 1 and BS to eavesdropper	No
[9]	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Jamming signal is added to the superimposed signal by BS	No
[10]	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Jamming signal is produced by the user with weaker channel condition to secure his data from the internal eavesdropper	No
[11]	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	UAV act like a relay here and introducing a jamming link to eavesdropper	Yes
[12]	Yes	No	Yes	No	Jammer produces interference link to both users and eavesdropper	Yes
Proposed work	Yes	Yes (stronger user helps the weaker one in 2^{nd} time slot)	Yes	Yes	No	Yes

1. In general, for the K number of users average channel gains of the users can be written as: $|h_1|^2 < |h_2|^2 < \dots < |h_{Ke}|^2 < |h_e|^2 < |h_{Ke+1}|^2 < \dots < |h_K|^2$. Due to the superimposed nature of P-NOMA, message signals of all users are superimposed and transmitted at the BS. The user with the highest power allocation factor will be introducing a huge amount of interference to the user with the highest average channel gain. The user with a greater average channel condition will first apply the SIC in which the signal of highest power will be detected, and subtracted from the received signal. The signal of the weaker user has already been detected thus the weaker user can be assisted by the stronger user accordingly. In this scenario, the eavesdropper will experience two transmission phases i.e., one direct phase transmission from BS and a second cooperative phase in which the stronger user helps the weaker user. The stronger user is facing huge interference; therefore, its message is considered safe from an eavesdropper, but the channel of the weaker user can easily be exploited. The weaker user in both the phases is considered for the secrecy rate maximization under constraints on QoS on the stronger legitimate user and the total power.

Transmitted signal in wireless communication is formulated as:

$$y = hx + n, \quad (1)$$

Where y represents the transmitted signal by the BS, h is

the channel assigned to the superimposed signal x under the presence of Additive White Gaussian Noise (AWGN) denoted by n .

A. Direct Transmission Phase

In the direct transmission phase, information signals of both the users are superimposed and broadcast from the BS. Eq.1 can be written as:

$$y_k^1 = h_k \sum_{i=1}^K \left(\sqrt{P_T \beta_i} x_i \right) + n_k^1, \quad (2)$$

where y_k^1 is the broadcast signal, P_T is the total power, β_i is the power allocation factor of i th user, x_i is the signal of i th user and n_k is the AWGN and can be written as $n \sim N(0, \sigma^2)$. Achievable rate for K th user can be written as:

$$R_K^1 = \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{|h_K|^2 P_T \beta_K}{\sigma_{K,1}^2} \right), \quad (3)$$

where, $|h_K|^2$ is the average channel condition of K th user, and $\sigma_{(K,1)}^2$ is the variance of AWGN. Now, for m th user which lies somewhere between user 1 and user K i.e.

$1 < m < K$. Achievable rate can be written as:

$$R_m^1 = \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{|h_m|^2 P_T \beta_m}{\sum_{i=m+1}^K P_T \beta_i |h_m|^2 + \sigma_{m,1}^2} \right), \quad (4)$$

Fig. 1. Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access in two users scenario

B. Cooperative Phase

In this phase, the detected signal of the weaker user during the SIC process is decoded and re-transmitted to the weaker user. By a generalization of the two user scenarios to the K number of users, it is observed that $K - 1$ users will help the farthest user. Therefore, $(K - 1)$ time slots will be needed to combine the received signals. The broadcast signal in this phase can be represented as:

$$y_k^2 = g_k \sum_{i=1}^{K-1} \left(\sqrt{P_c \gamma_i} x_i \right) + n_{k,2}^2, \quad (5)$$

The achievable rate for K th user in the cooperative phase can be written as:

$$R_K^2 = \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{|g_k|^2 P_c \gamma_K}{\sigma_{K,2}^2} \right), \quad (6)$$

where γ is the power allocation factor, and P_c is the total power transmitted in phase 2 of D-NOMA communication system.

C. Secrecy Rate

According to Shannon [14], secrecy rate is the difference of the achievable rates of legitimate users and eavesdroppers. In our case secrecy rate is:

$$R_s = [R_K - R_e]^+, \quad (7)$$

where R_s is the Shannon's secrecy capacity and $\{x\}^+$ shows the supremum of x . In the 1st of NOMA communication, achievable rate of eavesdropper can be written as:

$$R_e^1 = \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{|h_e|^2 P_T \beta_e}{\sigma_{e,2}^2} \right) \quad (8)$$

According to eq.7, secrecy rate for K th user in 1st phase of D-NOMA communication, after simplification, can be written as:

$$R_s^1 = \log_2 \left(\frac{\left(1 + \frac{|h_m|^2 P_T \beta_m}{\sum_{i=m+1}^K P_T \beta_i |h_m|^2 + \sigma_{m,1}^2} \right)}{\left(1 + \frac{|h_e|^2 P_T \beta_e}{\sigma_{e,2}^2} \right)} \right) \quad (9)$$

According to the superposition nature of NOMA, the strongest average channel condition user is already facing huge interference caused by the user having the highest power allocation factor. This interference allows us to assume the strongest user as safe from the eavesdropper. The eq.9 for 1st phase can be re-arranged as:

$$R_s^1 = \log_2 \left(\frac{\left(1 + \frac{|h_1|^2 P_T \beta_1}{P_T \beta_2 |h_2|^2 + \sigma_{1,1}^2} \right)}{\left(1 + \frac{|h_e|^2 P_T \beta_e}{\sigma_{e,1}^2} \right)} \right) \quad (10)$$

In the second phase of D-NOMA, the maximum achievable rate of the eavesdropper can be written as:

$$R_e^2 = \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{|g_e|^2 P_c \gamma_e}{\sigma_{2,2}^2} \right) \quad (11)$$

Using eq.6 and eq.11, the secrecy rate eq.7 for second phase of D-NOMA can be written as:

$$R_s^2 = \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{|g_k|^2 P_c \gamma_K}{\sigma_{K,2}^2} \right) - \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{|g_e|^2 P_c \gamma_e}{\sigma_{2,2}^2} \right) \quad (12)$$

which can be re-arranged as:

$$R_s^2 = \log_2 \left(\frac{\left(1 + \frac{|g_k|^2 P_c \gamma_K}{\sigma_{K,2}^2} \right)}{\left(1 + \frac{|g_e|^2 P_c \gamma_e}{\sigma_{2,2}^2} \right)} \right) \quad (13)$$

These equations are the mathematical representations of achievable rates of legitimate users in the proposed system model i.e. 1st phase of transmission as well as 2nd phase of transmission. The secrecy rate is found in the following section for maximization.

IV. SECRECY RATE MAXIMIZATION

The expressions for the legitimate users and eavesdroppers are derived in the above section. Now, we have to maximize the secrecy rate of the weaker user in the direct transmission phase of D-NOMA. The secrecy rate of the user with weaker average channel condition of both

phases is summed and is called Sum Secrecy Rate (SSR). Mathematical representation is as follows:

$$Rs = \sum_{i=1}^2 Rs^i \quad (14)$$

The objective of this work is to maximize the SSR, which can be mathematically represented as:

$$\max \left(\sum_{i=1}^2 Rs^i \right) \quad (15a)$$

Subject to:

$$\sum_{i=1}^K \beta_i = 1 \quad (15b)$$

$$R_i \geq Q_i \quad (15c)$$

$$\sum_{i=m}^K \gamma_i = 1 \quad (15d)$$

Equation 15c can be re-arranged as:

$$\beta_1 \geq \left(\frac{|h_2|^2 \beta_2 P_T + \sigma_{1,2}^2}{|h_2|^2 P_T} \right) (2^{Q_2} - 1) \quad (16)$$

In the proposed model, we assume $\Gamma_{l,m}$ as Signal to Noise and Interference Ratio (SINR) of user l in m phase of D-NOMA. i.e.,

$$\Gamma_{1,1} = \frac{\beta_1 |h_1|^2 P_T}{\beta_2 |h_2|^2 P_T + \sigma_{1,1}^2}, \quad (17)$$

$$\Gamma_{2,1} = \frac{\beta_2 |h_2|^2 P_T}{\sigma_{2,1}^2}, \quad (18)$$

$$\Gamma_{1,2} = \frac{\gamma_1 |g_1|^2 P_c}{\sigma_{1,2}^2}, \quad (19)$$

$$\Gamma_{e,1} = \frac{\beta_e |h_e|^2 P_T}{\beta_2 |h_2|^2 P_T + \sigma_{2,1}^2}, \quad (20)$$

$$\Gamma_{e,2} = \frac{\gamma_e |g_e|^2 P_c}{\sigma_{e,2}^2}, \quad (21)$$

where $\Gamma_{1,1}, \Gamma_{2,1}, \Gamma_{1,2}, \Gamma_{e,1}$ and $\Gamma_{e,2}$ represents the SINR of user 1 in 1st phase, SINR of user 2 in 1st phase, SINR of user 1 in 2nd phase, SINR of eavesdropper in 1st phase and SINR of eavesdropper in 2nd phase, respectively. Now, using eqs. 17, 18, 19, 20, and 21, objective function i.e. eq.15a is re-arranged as:

$$Rs = \log_2 \left(\frac{(\Gamma_{1,1} + 1)(\Gamma_{1,2} + 1)}{(\Gamma_{e,1} + 1)(\Gamma_{e,2} + 1)} \right) \quad (22)$$

R_s is maximized using the Lagrangian Optimization method. The Lagrangian of eq.15a using eq.22 is derived as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}(\beta_1, \beta_2, \gamma_1, \lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3) = & \log_2 \left(\frac{(\Gamma_{1,1} + 1)(\Gamma_{1,2} + 1)}{(\Gamma_{e,1} + 1)(\Gamma_{e,2} + 1)} \right) \\ & + \lambda_1 \left(\beta_2 - (2^{Q_2} - 1) \left(\frac{\sigma_{2,1}^2}{|h_2|^2 P_T} \right) \right) + \\ & \lambda_2 (1 - \beta_1 - \beta_2) + \lambda_3 (1 - \gamma_1) \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

Substituting the values of $R_s, \Gamma_{1,1}, \Gamma_{1,2}, \Gamma_{e,1}$ and $\Gamma_{e,2}$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}(\beta_1, \beta_2, \gamma_1, \lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3) = & \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{\beta_1 |h_1|^2 P_T}{\beta_2 |h_2|^2 P_T + \sigma_{1,1}^2} + \frac{\gamma_1 |g_1|^2 P_c}{\sigma_{1,2}^2} \right) - \\ & \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{\beta_e |h_e|^2 P_T}{\beta_2 |h_2|^2 P_T + \sigma_{2,1}^2} + \frac{\gamma_e |g_e|^2 P_c}{\sigma_{e,2}^2} \right) + \\ & \lambda_1 \left(\beta_2 - (2^{Q_2} - 1) \left(\frac{\sigma_{2,1}^2}{|h_2|^2 P_T} \right) \right) + \\ & \lambda_2 (1 - \beta_1 - \beta_2) + \lambda_3 (1 - \gamma_1) \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

Let

$$F = \mathcal{L}(\beta_1, \beta_2, \gamma_1, \lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3)$$

Now, differentiating F with respect to $\beta_1, \beta_2, \gamma_1, \lambda_1, \lambda_2$ and λ_3 respectively,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dF}{d\beta_1} = & \log_2 e \left(\frac{1}{1 + \frac{\beta_1 |h_1|^2 P_T}{\beta_2 |h_2|^2 P_T + \sigma_{1,1}^2} + \frac{\gamma_1 |g_1|^2 P_c}{\sigma_{1,2}^2}} \right) \\ & \left(\frac{|h_1|^2 P_T}{\beta_2 |h_2|^2 P_T + \sigma_{1,1}^2} \right) + \lambda_2 \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dF}{d\beta_2} = & \log_2 e \left(\frac{1}{1 + \frac{\beta_1 |h_1|^2 P_T}{\beta_2 |h_2|^2 P_T + \sigma_{1,1}^2} + \frac{\gamma_1 |g_1|^2 P_c}{\sigma_{1,2}^2}} \right) \\ & \left(\frac{-\beta_1 |h_1|^4 P_T^2}{(\beta_2 |h_2|^2 P_T + \sigma_{1,1}^2)^2} \right) - \\ & \log_2 e \left(\frac{1}{1 + \frac{\beta_e |h_e|^2 P_T}{\beta_2 |h_2|^2 P_T + \sigma_{2,1}^2} + \frac{\gamma_e |g_e|^2 P_c}{\sigma_{e,2}^2}} \right) \\ & \left(\frac{-\beta_e |h_e|^4 P_T^2}{(\beta_2 |h_2|^2 P_T + \sigma_{2,1}^2)^2} \right) + \lambda_1 + \lambda_2 \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dF}{d\gamma_1} = & \log_2 e \left(\frac{1}{1 + \frac{\beta_1 |h_1|^2 P_T}{\beta_2 |h_2|^2 P_T + \sigma_{1,1}^2} + \frac{\gamma_1 |g_1|^2 P_c}{\sigma_{1,2}^2}} \right) \\ & \left(\frac{|g_1|^2 P_c}{\sigma_{1,2}^2} \right) + \lambda_3 \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

In order to find λ_2 , put eq.25 equals to zero. We get:

$$\lambda_2 = \left(-\frac{|h_1|^2 P_T}{\beta_2 |h_2|^2 P_T + \sigma_{1,1}^2} \right) \log_2 e \left(\frac{1}{1 + \frac{\beta_1 |h_1|^2 P_T}{\beta_2 |h_2|^2 P_T + \sigma_{1,1}^2} + \frac{\gamma_1 |g_1|^2 P_c}{\sigma_{1,2}^2}} \right) \quad (28)$$

In order to find λ_1 , put eq.26 equals to zero and substitute eq.28, we get;

$$\lambda_1 = \left(\frac{\beta_1 |h_1|^4 P_T^2}{(\beta_2 |h_2|^2 P_T + \sigma_{1,1}^2)^2} \right) \log_2 e \left(\frac{1}{1 + \frac{\beta_1 |h_1|^2 P_T}{\beta_2 |h_2|^2 P_T + \sigma_{1,1}^2} + \frac{\gamma_1 |g_1|^2 P_c}{\sigma_{1,2}^2}} \right) - \left(\frac{\beta_e |h_e|^4 P_T^2}{(\beta_2 |h_2|^2 P_T + \sigma_{e,1}^2)^2} \right) \log_2 e \left(\frac{1}{1 + \frac{\beta_e |h_e|^2 P_T}{\beta_2 |h_2|^2 P_T + \sigma_{e,1}^2} + \frac{\gamma_e |g_e|^2 P_c}{\sigma_{e,2}^2}} \right) + \left(-\frac{|h_1|^2 P_T}{\beta_2 |h_2|^2 P_T + \sigma_{1,1}^2} \right) \log_2 e \left(\frac{1}{1 + \frac{\beta_1 |h_1|^2 P_T}{\beta_2 |h_2|^2 P_T + \sigma_{1,1}^2} + \frac{\gamma_1 |g_1|^2 P_c}{\sigma_{1,2}^2}} \right) \quad (29)$$

Similarly, from eq.27, λ_3 is found as:

$$\lambda_3 = \left(-\frac{|g_1|^2 P_c}{\sigma_{1,2}^2} \right) \log_2 e \left(\frac{1}{1 + \frac{\beta_1 |h_1|^2 P_T}{\beta_2 |h_2|^2 P_T + \sigma_{1,1}^2} + \frac{\gamma_1 |g_1|^2 P_c}{\sigma_{1,2}^2}} \right) \quad (30)$$

The following algorithm is implemented for finding of optimum value of λ_1 , λ_2 and λ_3 .

Fig. 2. Convergence of λ_1 and λ_2

Algorithm 1: algorithm of finding optimum values of β_1 and β_2

Output: β_1, β_2

- 1 **Initialization:**
 - 2 $\beta_1 \leftarrow 0.1$ // Power Allocation factor of UE1
 - 3 $\beta_2 \leftarrow 1 - \beta_1$ // Power Allocation factor of UE2
 - 4 $\lambda_1 \leftarrow 0.1$ // Lagrange Multiplier for constraint 1
 - 5 $\lambda_2 \leftarrow 0.1$ // Lagrange Multiplier for constraint 2
 - 6 $\lambda_3 \leftarrow 0.1$ // Lagrange Multiplier for constraint 3
 - 7 $|h_i| \leftarrow randn(1, N) + j * randn(1, N)$ // Random channels of $1 \times N$
 - 8 **while** *Until* λ *converges* **do**
 - 9 λ_1, λ_2 and $\lambda_3 \leftarrow$ compute using above equations respectively // Using initial conditions on the first go
 - 10 β_1 and $\beta_2 \leftarrow$ compute using new values of λ_1, λ_2 and λ_3 // Optimum value on the convergence
 - 11 $i \leftarrow i + 1$ // update iteration counter
 - end**
 - 12 $Rs_1 \leftarrow$ Compute 22 using optimum values of β_i and λ_i // Secrecy rate of user with weaker channel condition
-

Fig. 2 shows the convergence graph of λ . In the first 100-150 iterations out of 1000, the graph appears to be smooth due to the availability of only so many pixels. Tracing along the curve reveals that λ is approaching the point of

convergence i.e., β . The values of β_i where λ converges are: $\beta_1 = 0.69, \beta_2 = 0.31$ and $\gamma = 1$.

V. SIMULATIONS AND RESULTS DISCUSSION

The proposed system model consists of a source and two D-NOMA users considering direct communication with both the users in the 1st phase of D-NOMA. In the second phase of D-NOMA, the decoded message of the weaker user is forwarded to the weaker user. All the channels are assumed to be quasi-static fading channels; furthermore, h_i represents the channel of i_{th} user in the first phase of D-NOMA. Similarly, g_i represents the channel of i_{th} user in the second phase of D-NOMA. Fading coefficients are kept constant for each of the channels during the transmission of each codeword but can be changed randomly after each transmission. The user with the worst channel condition will receive two signals, one from the BS and the other from the user with a better channel condition who is going to act like a relay. So, there are two phases of reception for the user with the worst channel condition. The parameters used in the simulations are depicted in the table II.

A. Optimization of the Secrecy Rate

In the first phase of D-NOMA, received SNRs on both legitimate user and eavesdropper are given in eq.17 and eq.20, respectively. σ^2 is the variance of AWGN and kept constant during simulation i.e. $N_o = -60$ dBm and h_i is $CN \sim (0,1)$. The secrecy rate of users with weaker channel conditions in phase one of NOMA is plotted, we observed that the secrecy rate is increased with increasing the power. Fig.3 shows that when transmitting power of 30dBm is assigned, the secrecy rate achieved is 0.06 bits per second per hertz (bps/h), while the optimized value is 1 bps/h. 30dBm is not a fixed value, it depends on the user pairing of D-NOMA. The power is assigned to the weaker user in a manner that the QoS of the strong user is satisfied. After finding out the secrecy rate in phase one and phase two of NOMA, the user with weaker channel condition has two-time slots, in the first-time slot user receives a superimposed signal from BS, and in the second time slot, the user receives a signal from user with stronger channel condition. The secrecy rate for user 1 of the system is found. In this situation, the capacity of user 1 is the minimum of capacities received from both phases. Mathematical representation can be as follows:

$$R_1 = \min \{ \log_2 (1 + \Gamma_{1,1}), \log_2 (1 + \Gamma_{1,2}) \} \quad (31)$$

The secrecy rate has been maximized as shown in Fig. 3. The optimized and non-optimized secrecy rates can be compared. The vertical axis represents the secrecy rate in bps/h, whereas the horizontal axis shows the power in dBm. The secrecy rate of the weaker user is maximized sustaining the QoS of the stronger user.

Fig. 3. Optimized Secrecy sum rate and non-optimized secrecy sum rate in D-NOMA

TABLE II
SIMULATION PARAMETERS

S.No	Description	Symbols	Values
1	Channel Model	h	Complex Gaussian $CN(0, 1)$
2	Noise Variance	σ	-60 dBm for each node
3	Power	P_T	35 dBm
4	Power Allocation Factor of User 1	β_1	0.69
5	Power Allocation Factor of User 2	β_2	0.31
6	Power Allocation Factor in 2 nd Phase	γ_1	1
7	Value of Lagrange Multiplier	λ_1	0.0489
8	Value of Lagrange Multiplier	λ_2	0.1048

VI. CONCLUSION

We presented the NOMA resource allocation mechanism ensuring physical layer security. Two phases of transmissions are considered i.e., transmission from BS to UEs and transmission from strong legitimate users to weak legitimate users. It is assumed that the eavesdropper is not able to decode the message of the strong user due to high interference. The secrecy rate of the weak user is investigated, and a closed-form expression for secrecy rate maximization in the presence of an eavesdropper with optimal power allocation factors is derived. Our results show that the QoS of the legitimate users are kept up to the predefined level and the secrecy rate of the weaker user is maximized using the Lagrangian function. The user pairing in this cooperative nature of NOMA for resource optimization ensuring a certain level of secrecy rate is considered as a possible extension of this study in the future.

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